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A Review About Big Data Issues and Challenges

ABSTRACT

Big data refers to data volumes in the range of Exabyte and beyond. Such volumes exceed the capacity of current on-line storage systems and processing systems. Data, information, and knowledge are being created and collected at a rate that is rapidly approaching the Exabyte/year range. But, its creation and aggregation are accelerating and will approach the zettabyte/year range within a few years. Volume is only one aspect of big data; other attributes are variety, velocity, value, and complexity. Storage and data transport are technology issues, which seem to be solvable in the near-term, but represent long term challenges that require research and new paradigms. Recent technological advancements have led to a deluge of data from distinctive domains (e.g., health care and scientific sensors, user-generated data, Internet and financial companies, and supply chain systems) over the past two decades. The term big data was coined to capture the meaning of this emerging trend. In addition to its sheer volume, big data also exhibits other unique characteristics as compared with traditional data. For instance, big data is commonly unstructured and require more real-time analysis. This development calls for new system architectures for data acquisition, transmission, storage, and large-scale data processing mechanisms. In this paper we analyzing the issues and parameters of big data.

KEYWORDS

Data Issues and Challenges, Data Volume, traditional database.

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INTRODUCTION: Over the past 20 years, data has increased in a large scale in various fields. According to a report from International Data Corporation (IDC), in 2011, the overall created and copied data volume in the world was 1.8ZB ($\approx 1021B$), which increased by nearly nine times within five years [1]. This figure will double at least every other two years in the near future. Under the explosive increase of global data, the term of big data is mainly used to describe enormous data sets. Compared with traditional datasets, big data typically includes masses of unstructured data that need more real-time analysis. In addition, big data also brings about new opportunities for discovering new values, helps us to gain an in-depth understanding of the hidden values, and also incurs new challenges, e.g., how to effectively organize and manage such datasets. Recently, industries become interested in the high potential of big data, and many government agencies announced major plans to accelerate big data research and applications [2]. In addition, issues on big data are often covered in public media, such as The Economist [3, 4], New York Times [5], and National Public Radio [6, 7]. Two premier scientific journals, Nature and Science, also opened special columns to discuss the challenges and impacts of big data [8, 9]. The era of big data has come beyond all doubt [10]. Nowadays, big data related to the service of Internet companies grow rapidly. Generates data of tens of Terabyte (TB) for online trading per day. Figure 1 illustrates the boom of the global data volume. While the amount of large data sets is drastically rising, it also brings about many challenging problems demanding prompt solutions.

The concept of big data has been endemic within

computer science since the earliest days of computing. “Big Data” originally meant the volume of data that could not be processed (efficiently) by traditional database methods and tools. Each time a new storage medium was invented, the amount of data accessible exploded because it could be easily accessed. The original definition focused on structured data, but most researchers and practitioners have come to realize that most of the world’s information resides in massive, unstructured information, largely in the form of text and imagery. The explosion of data has not been accompanied by a corresponding new storage medium. We define “Big Data” as the amount of data just beyond technology’s capability to store, manage and process efficiently. These imitations are only discovered by a robust analysis of the data itself, explicit processing needs, and the capabilities of the tools (hardware, software, and methods) used to analyze it. As with any new problem, the conclusion of how to proceed may lead to a recommendation that new tools need to be forged to perform the new tasks. As little as 5 years ago, we were only thinking of tens to hundreds of gigabytes of storage for our personal computers. Today, we are thinking in tens to hundreds of terabytes. Thus, big data is a moving target. Put another way, it is that amount of data that is just beyond our immediate grasp, e.g., we have to work hard to store it, access it, manage it, and process it. The current growth rate in the amount of data collected is staggering. A major challenge for IT researchers and practitioners is that this growth rate is fast exceeding our ability to both: (1) design appropriate systems to handle the data effectively and (2) and analyze it to extract relevant meaning for decision making. In this paper we identify critical issues associated with data storage, management, and processing. To the best of our knowledge, the research literature has not effectively addressed these issues. Big data is an abstract concept. Apart from masses of data, it also has some other features, which determine the difference between itself and “massive data” or “very big data.” At present, although the importance of big data has been generally recognized, people still have different opinions on its definition. In general, big data shall mean the datasets that could not be perceived, acquired, managed, and processed by traditional IT and software/hardware tools within a tolerable time. Because of different concerns, scientific and technological enterprises, research scholars, data analysts, and technical practitioners have different definitions of big data.

In August 2010, the White House, OMB, and OSTP proclaimed that Big Data is a national challenge and priority along with healthcare and national security [1]. The National Science Foundation, the National Institutes of Health, the U.S. Geological Survey, the Departments of Defense and Energy, and the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency announced a joint R&D initiative in March 2012 that will invest more than \$200 million to develop new big data tools and techniques. Its goal is to advance our “. Understanding of the technologies needed to manipulate and mine massive amounts of information; apply that knowledge to other scientific fields “as well as address the national goals in the areas of health energy defense, education and researcher”.

Recently, the big data emerged as a hot topic because of the tremendous growth of the information and communication technology. One of the highly anticipated key contributors of the big data in the future networks is the distributed wireless sensor networks (WSNs). Although the data generated by an individual sensor may not appear to be significant, the overall data generated across numerous sensors in the densely distributed WSNs can produce a significant portion of the big data. Energy-efficient big data gathering in the densely distributed sensor networks is, therefore, a challenging research area. One of the most effective solutions to address this challenge is to utilize the sink node’s mobility to facilitate the data gathering. While this technique can reduce energy consumption of the sensor nodes, the use of mobile sink presents additional challenges such as determining the sink node’s trajectory and cluster formation prior to data collection. In this paper, we propose a new mobile sink routing and data gathering method through network clustering based on modified expectation maximization technique.

Big Data Characteristics: Data Volume: Data volume measures the amount of data available to an organization, which does not necessarily have to own all of it as long as it can access it. As data volume increases, the value of different data records will decrease in proportion to age, type, richness, and quantity among other factors.

Data Velocity: Data velocity measures the speed of data creation, streaming, and aggregation. Ecommerce has rapidly increased the speed and richness of data used for different business transactions (for example, web-site clicks). Data velocity management is much more than a bandwidth issue; it is also an ingest issue (extract transform-load).

Data Variety: Data variety is a measure of the richness of the data representation – text, images video, audio, etc. From an analytic perspective, it is probably the biggest obstacle to effectively using large volumes of data. Incompatible data formats, non-aligned data structures, and inconsistent data semantics represents significant challenges that can lead to analytic sprawl.

Data Value: Data value measures the usefulness of data in making decisions. It has been noted that “the purpose of computing is insight, not numbers”. Data science is exploratory and useful in getting to know the data, but “analytic science” encompasses the predictive power of big data.

Complexity: Complexity measures the degree of interconnectedness (possibly very large) and interdependence in big data structures such that a small change (or combination of small changes) in one or a few elements can yield very large changes or a small change that ripple across or cascade through the system and substantially affect its behavior, or no change at all.

Major challenges and issues in big data: We suggest there are three fundamental issue areas that need to be addressed in dealing with big data: storage issues, management issues, and processing issues. Each of these represents a large set of technical research problems in its own right.

Storage and Transport Issues: The quantity of data has exploded each time we have invented a new storage medium. What is different about the most recent explosion – due largely to social media – is that there has been no new storage medium. Moreover, data is being created by everyone and everything (e.g., devices, etc.) – not just, as heretofore, by professionals such as scientist, journalists, writers, etc.

Current disk technology limits are about 4 terabytes per disk. So, 1 exabyte would require 25,000 disks. Even if an exabyte of data could be processed on a single computer system, it would be unable to directly attach the requisite number of disks. Access to that data would overwhelm current communication networks. Assuming that a 1 gigabyte per second network has an effective sustainable transfer rate of 80%, the sustainable bandwidth is about 100 megabytes. Thus, transferring an exabyte would take about 2800 hours, if we assume that a sustained transfer could be maintained. It would take longer to transmit the data from a collection or storage point to a processing point than it would to actually process it! Two solutions manifest themselves. First, process the data “in place” and transmit only the resulting information. In other words, “bring the code to the data”, vs. the traditional method of “bring the data to the code.” Second, perform triage on the data and transmit only that data which is critical to downstream analysis. In case, integrity and provenance metadata should be transmitted along with the actual data.

Management Issues: Management will, perhaps, be the most difficult problem to address with big data. This problem first surfaced a decade ago in the UK eScience initiatives where data was distributed geographically and “owned” and “managed” by multiple entities. Resolving issues of

access, metadata, utilization, updating, governance, and reference (in publications) have proven to be major stumbling blocks. Unlike the collection of data by manual methods, where rigorous protocols are often followed in order to ensure accuracy and validity, digital data collection is much more relaxed. The richness of digital data representation prohibits a bespoke methodology for data collection. Data qualification often focuses more on missing data or outliers than trying to validate every item. Data is often very fine-grained such as clickstream or metering data. Given the volume, it is impractical to validate every data item: new approaches to data qualification and validation are needed. The sources of this data are varied - both temporally and spatially, by format, and by method of collection. Individuals contribute digital data in mediums comfortable to them: documents, drawings, pictures, sound and video recordings, models, software behaviors, user interface designs, etc. - with or without adequate metadata describing what, when, where, who, why and how it was collected and its provenance. Yet, all this data is readily available for inspection and analysis. "We are unaware of any robust, open source, platform independent solution to this problem." As far as we know, this remains true today. To summarize, there is no perfect big data management solution yet. This represents an important gap in the research literature on big data that needs to be filled.

Processing Issues: Assume that an Exabyte of data needs to be processed in its entirety. For simplicity, assume the data is chunked into blocks of 8 words, so 1 Exabyte = 1K petabytes. Assuming a processor expends 100 instructions on one block at 5 gigahertz, the time required for end-to-end processing would be 20 nanoseconds. To process 1K petabytes would require a total end-to-end processing time of roughly 635 years. Thus, effective processing of Exabyte of data will require extensive parallel processing and new analytics algorithms in order to provide timely and actionable information.

Dynamic Design Challenges: There are numerous challenges requiring long term research to working with big data. Stonebreaker and Hong [18] argue that the design for the systems and components that work with big data will require an understanding of both the needs of the users and the technologies that can be used to solve the problem being investigated - i.e., not all big data and its requirements are the same. In this instance, since the data that is newly created (envisioned and collected), is neither truly known nor well understood, designers will need to consider interfaces, graphics, and icons; application organization; and conceptual models, metaphors, and functionality. Because the end users will not often be the system designers, this presents an additional design challenge. There are unknown challenges that will arise with each increase in scale and development of new analytics. Some of these challenges will be impracticable with the tools and techniques at hand. We believe these challenges to be just "over the horizon" with the next jump to zettabyte-size data sets.

Compliance and Security: In certain domains, such as social media and health information, as more data is accumulated about individuals, there is a fear that certain organizations will know too much about individuals. For example, data collected in electronic health record systems in accordance with HIPAA/HITECH provisions is already raising concerns about violations of one's privacy. Developing algorithms that randomize personal data among a large data set enough to ensure privacy is a key research problem. Perhaps the biggest threat to personal security is the unregulated accumulation of data by numerous social media companies. This data represents a severe security concern, especially when many individuals so willingly surrender such information. Questions of accuracy, dissemination, expiration, and access abound. For example, the State of Maryland became the first state to prohibit by law employers asking for Facebook and other social media passwords during employment interviews and afterwards. International Data Corporation

(IDC) coined the term “digital shadow” to reflect the amount of data concerning an individual which has been collected, organized, and perhaps analyzed, to form an aggregate “picture” of the individual. It is the information about you that is much greater than the information you create and/or release about yourself. A key problem is how much of this information – either original or derived – do we want to remain private? Clearly, some big data must be secured with respect to privacy and security laws and regulations. IDC suggested five levels of increasing security [8]: privacy, compliance-driven, custodial, confidential, and lockdown. Further research is required to clearly define these security levels and map them against both current law and current analytics.

Conclusion: Big data is the “new” business and social science frontier. The amount of information and knowledge that can be extracted from the digital universe is continuing to expand as users come up with new ways to massage and process data. Moreover, it has become clear that “more data is not just more data”, but that “more data is different”. “Big data” is just the beginning of the problem. Technology evolution and placement guarantee that in a few years more data will be available in a year than has been collected since the dawn of man. If Facebook and Twitter are producing, collectively, around 50 gigabytes of data per day, and tripling every year, within a few years (perhaps 3-5) we are indeed facing the challenge of “big data becoming really big data”. In this paper we address the common issues and challenges of big data.

REFERENCES:

- American Institute of Physics (AIP). 2010. College Park, MD, (<http://www.aip.org/fyi/2010/>)
- [2] Ayres, I. 2007. *Super crunchers*, Bantam Books, New York, NY
- Boyd, D. and K. Crawford. 2011. “Six Provocations for Big Data”, Oxford Internet Institute’s “A Decade in Internet Time: Symposium on the Dynamics of the Internet and Society”
- The Economist. 2010. “Data, Data Everywhere”, (online edition, February 28)
<http://www.economist.com/node/15557443>
- Felten, E. 2010. “Needle in a Haystack Problems”, <https://freedom-to-tinker.com/blog/felten/needle-haystackproblems/>
- Fox, B. 2011. “Leveraging Big Data for Big Impact”, Health Management Technology,
<http://www.healthmgttech.com/>
- Freeman, K. 2011. http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Kencf0618Facebook_Network.jpg
- Gantz, J. and E. Reinsel. 2011. “Extracting Value from Chaos”, IDC’s Digital Universe Study, sponsored by EMC
- Jacobs, A. 2009. “Pathologies of Big Data”, *Communications of the ACM*, 52(8):36-44
- JASON. 2008. “Data Analysis Challenges”, The Mitre Corporation, McLean, VA, JSR-08-142
- Kaisler, S. 2012. “Advanced Analytics”, CATALYST Technical Report, i_SW Corporation, Arlington, VA
- Kaisler, S., W. Money, and S. J. Cohen. 2012. “A Decision Framework for Cloud Computing”, 45th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, Grand Wailea, Maui, HI, Jan 4-7, 2012
- Kang, U. 2012. “Mining Tera-scale Graphs with MapReduce: Theory, Engineering, and Discoveries”, PhD. Thesis, Computer Science, Carnegie-Mellon University, Pittsburgh, PA
- Mervis, J. 2012. “Agencies Rally to Tackle Big Data”, *Science*, 336(4):22, June 6, 2012